

SECOND REPORT

PERIOD: 30 SEPTEMBER 2019 – 19TH OCTOBER 2020

PROJECTS

- THE CONSTRUCTION OF FOUR UNITS OF SQUAT TOILETS AT LEA TAKUSHARA & LEA KUNYAMI COMMUNITY SCHOOLS
- THE DRILLING OF BOREHOLES & THE INSTALLATION OF HANDPUMPS AT EACH SCHOOL
- THE PRINTING AND DISTRIBUTION OF EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ON BASIC HYGIENE AT EACH SCHOOL

LEA KUNYAMI

WATER PROJECT:

After geological surveys were conducted, water was found at a 60-70meter depth. A 60-70meter borehole was then drilled and covered at the LEA School Kunyami and LEA Takushara.

Both school sites showed adequate water levels and access.

TOILET PROJECT:

4 squat toilet units constructed and completed for the elementary school at Kunyami.

HANDPUMP PURCHASE AND INSTALLATION:

Hand pumps were purchased and installed in the schools.

PRINTING OF HEALTH EDUCATION MATERIALS FOR THE PUPILS

Health Education Materials were printed for hand washing and hygiene sensitization for the pupils.

PROJECT HANDOVER & COMMISSIONING

The project was commissioned and handed over to the school. In attendance were representatives from Universal Basic Education Board in Abuja, The Education secretary, of the LEA Board, The community representative and the staff of the school and the happy pupils of the school.

PUBLIC HEALTH AID AWARENESS &
EDUCATION ORGANIZATION
(PHAAE)
IN COLLABORATION WITH THE U.S. GOVERNMENT

Invites You to the
Commissioning Ceremony
of Her Projects

**4 UNITS TOILET &
A WATER FACILITY**

 Today, October The 12th, 2020
 11:00am Prompt

 LEA Kunyami, FCT Abuja

LEA TAKUSHARA

WATER PROJECT:

After the geological survey, 70-90meter borehole was drilled and covered. The site showed great water level and presence of adequate water for hand pumps.

TOILET PROJECT:

8 units of toilets for the pupils and teachers were in a dilapidated state and not in use at LEA Takushara.

Inquired with the head teacher as to the action to take and what the school wanted, and the school requested a renovation of the broken down toilet facilities and buildings.

Project scope changed, and funds for building 4 new toilet units was used to renovate 2 buildings of 8 units toilets for pupils and teachers at LEA Takushara.

HAND PUMP PURCHASE & INSTALLATION:

Hand pump was purchased and installed.

PRINTING OF HEALTH EDUCATION MATERIALS

Health Education Materials were printed and distributed for health education purposes at the schools.

HANDOVER & COMMISSIONING OF PROJECTS

The project was commissioned and handed over to the school. And in attendance at the commissioning were the representative from the Nigerian Union of Teachers, Universal Basic Education Board, Education Secretary of the LEA Board, The traditional ruler of the Takushara community, Youth Representative of the Takushara community, the Parents Teachers Association leader, the head teacher, and the excited pupils of the school.

**PUBLIC HEALTH AID AWARENESS &
EDUCATION ORGANIZATION
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*Invites You to the
Commissioning Ceremony
of Her Projects*

**4 UNITS TOILET &
WATER BOREHOLE**

 Today, October The 14th, 2020

 11:00am Prompt

 LEA Takushara,, FCT Abuja

BARRIERS/DELAYS

A major delay and barrier that the team have worked around and rose above was the Pandemic and subsequent lockdown which affected businesses and rates, and caused an inflation in the rates of building materials and workmanship of the laborers.

CONCLUSION

The project is completed and commissioned. We thank the United States Ambassador for bringing smiles to the faces of these communities.